

Liquidity Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics Using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Literature Review

Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi
Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to determine the map of research development on liquidity risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The research was conducted for 17 years, from 2006 to 2022, by searching through the Scopus website for indexed international journals and Sinta for nationally accredited journals, using the keyword "Liquidity Risk". There are 289 research articles based on the search results. The search results are then analyzed descriptively, inputted, and analyzed with VOSviewer and literature review. The search results show that the number of publications has increased significantly yearly. Then, based on the mapping results using VOSviewer, research on liquidity risk is divided into 6 clusters. Based on the literature review study, there are 7 main themes about liquidity risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Liquidity Risk, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

INTRODUCTION

Global economic developments, especially in the sharia and conventional financial industry sectors, continue to move quickly, giving rise to increasingly complex risks. This causes the need for policies that manage risk exposure effectively and can control risks that will occur. In this way, the financial industry sector can continue to develop sustainably and stably even though it is hit by a financial crisis.

One of the risks that every financial institution needs to pay attention to is liquidity risk. Managing liquidity risk is very important because the impact of this risk is very large, in some cases there are even banks that fail as a result of not being able to meet liquidity needs. Liquidity risk can be caused by the bank being unable to generate cash flows from productive assets, or originating from the sale of assets including liquid assets, or from collecting public funds, interbank transactions or loans received. If at a time when liquidity is needed and the bank is unable to meet that liquidity need, for example from interbank loans, then the level of public trust will decrease. A further consequence of this is that it will cause liquidity problems, which in turn can affect other financial aspects that can threaten the continuity of the bank's business. So, banks must have adequate liquidity management plans to address these risks and ensure that they have sufficient funds to meet their short-term obligations. Banks are also required to meet liquidity requirements set by regulatory authorities to ensure that they can address liquidity risks.

Financial institutions need to implement liquidity risk management effectively, both individually and in consolidation with subsidiary companies, because liquidity problems can have a significant impact. In addition, the main objective of liquidity risk management is to ensure adequate funds on a daily basis, both in normal conditions and in crisis conditions in order to fulfill obligations in a timely manner from various available funding sources. Banks must estimate scheduled and unscheduled liquidity needs to maintain an efficient level of adequate liquidity. Procedures for managing liquidity risk are: (1) liquidity risk identification process to understand the bank's activity processes and identify nodes that are prone to liquidity risk problems; (2) measuring liquidity risk to determine the magnitude of liquidity risk and comparing it with the limit so that it can be decided whether a special strategy is needed to overcome problems related to liquidity risk; and (3) carry out liquidity risk control, in the form of actions needed to overcome problems related to liquidity risk.

Based on the problems above, mapping of liquidity risk management topics is needed to identify, measure and control risks that will occur. This can fulfill the need for human resources tasked with risk management to have knowledge, skills and work attitudes according to the bank's needs. So, the aim of this research is to map research topics around liquidity risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of

literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature review study to analyze, identify and review articles from international journals indexed by Scopus and national journals accredited by Sinta.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Liquidity risk is the risk faced by a bank that it will not be able to fulfill its obligations when they fall due due to difficulties in providing the necessary funds. This can happen because the bank does not have enough cash or assets that can be sold quickly to cover the obligations owed. This risk increases when the bank lends funds with a term that is longer than the term of the funds being lent. Liquidity risk may also arise from changes in interest rates, changes in customer preferences for withdrawing funds, or changes in banking regulations.

Bibliometric studies are the application of mathematical and statistical methods to the publication of books, articles and other information media. The aim is to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field. And can also analyze simple productivity indicators in research with more sophisticated and multidimensional techniques based on quotes in articles. So that it can identify and map new (multidisciplinary) scientific and technological developments.

VOSviewer is a software tool for creating, exploring and visualizing metadata network maps. It can be concluded that this device has two main functions:

- (1) Create bibliometric maps based on metadata networks. This map can create a network of scientific publications, journals, researchers, institutions, countries, keywords that are available or not yet available. To build this network, bibliographic database files are needed, such as Web of Science, Scopus, Dimensions, Lens and PubMed Files. Or from reference management files, such as RIS, EndNote, RefWorks Files) by inputting them into the software VOSviewer. And you can also download data via API, such as Crossref API, OpenAlex API, Europe PMC API and several others; And
- (2) Visualize and explore bibliometric maps. VOSviewer provides three forms of visualization, namely network, overlay and density visualization. The visualization can be enlarged making it possible to explore the bibliometric map in detail and completely, even if it contains thousands of items.

Literature review is the process of analyzing and identifying research articles on a particular theme. With this process, the steps for reviewing articles from journals, final assignments and seminar proceedings can be systematic and structured.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is liquidity risk in sharia and conventional banking. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on liquidity risk originating from international journals indexed by Scopus and national journals accredited by Sinta. The source of data collection comes from the website Scopus and Garuda (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish/Harzing software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Bank Liquidity Risk " for the entire year period (20 06 - 2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on literature review studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Liquidity Risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

Based on the results of data collection from the Perish/Harzing application during the period 2006 to 2022, there are 14 9 international journals indexed by Scopus and 15 0 Indonesian national journals indexed by Sinta regarding liquidity risk research in Financial Institutions. The average journal publication related to liquidity risk per year is around 18 articles.

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2006	1	2013	11	2018	28
2007	2	2014	12	2019	29
2009	5	2015	25	2020	35
2010	4	2016	12	2021	42
2011	4	2017	22	2022	50
2012	7				
Total 289					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

In table 2, there are 29 affiliates/institutions that publish the most journals regarding liquidity risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions. The IMF Economic Review is the largest journal publishing institution that publishes results on liquidity risk, with a total of 12 journal publications.

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
IMF Economic Review	12
EMBA Journal (Journal of Economic, Management, Business and Accounting Research)	7
Diponegoro Journal of Accounting	6
Banks and Bank Systems, Diponegoro Journal of Management	5
Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing, Journal of Economic & Business Dynamics, Journal of Banking and Finance, FEB Student Scientific Journal, Progress (Journal of Education, Accounting and Finance)	3
Asian Academy of Management Journal of Accounting and Finance, Cogent Economics and Finance, E-Jurnal Management, Fair Value (Scientific Journal of Accounting and Finance), International Review of Economics and Finance, Journal of Accounting and Investment, Journal of Financial Regulation and Compliance, Journal of Financial Stability, Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money, Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research, Journal of Money, Credit and Banking, Journal of Reviews on Global Economics, Journal of Theory and Applied Sharia Economics, Journal of Theory and Applied Management, Pacific Basin Finance Journal, Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance, Springer Proceedings in Business and Economics	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

In table 3, the menu shows the most productive researchers, namely: Syajarul Imna Moch. Amin from the Faculty of Economics and Management, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, who wrote 4 articles.

Researcher	Number of Publications
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Syajarul Imna Moch. Amen	4
Aisyah Abdul-Rahman	3
Chairul Adhim, Skender Ahmadi, Ameni Ghemini, Hasna Chaibi, Mohamed Ali Ibrahim Omri, Selva Demiralp, Olalere Oluwaseyi Ebenezer, Md. Aminul Islam, Wan Sallha Yusoff, Gatev Evan, Philip E. Strahan, Linda S. Goldberg, Omar Masood, Kiran Javaria, Rinda Siaga Pangestuti, Enrico Sette, Wei Yan, Yinghua Song, Nikolas, Topaloglou, Jan Willem van den End, Agnieszka Wojcik-Mazur,	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Liquidity Risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

Search results for articles on software Perish/Harzing are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around Liquidity Risk

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Software visualization results VOSViewer is related to the research development map regarding Liquidity Risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions, there are 6 clusters and 109 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1, red color consists of 39 topic items, namely: bank liquidity risk, bank sector, bank system, capital, case, CBS, commercial bank, conventional bank, credit, design methodology approach, economy, effectiveness, efficiency, financial crisis, financial institution, financial stability, fund, funding liquidity risk, gdp, ibs, inflation, Islamic bank, liquid asset, liquidity, liquidity ratio, liquidity risk management, literature, long run, management, market, measure, originality value, regulation, risk, role, rural bank, size, stability, term.
- Cluster 2, green, consists of 32 topic items, namely: ability, independent bank, banking company, banking financial performance, bopo, bpr, capital adequacy, company size, cost, credit risk, data, financial performance, financial services authority, financial statement, firm size, idx, indonesia stock exchange, insignificant effect, investor, islamic banking, ldr, market risk, nim, npl, operational risk, performing loan, persero, profitability, credit risk, liquidity risk, roa, state.
- Cluster 3, dark blue, consists of 14 topic items, namely: assets, banking, capital adequacy ratio, comparative study, conventional banking, covid, empirical evidence, equity, fdr, financing, risk, npf, return, roe.
- Cluster 4, yellow, consists of 13 topic items, namely: bank capital, bank performance, bank profitability, bank size, banking industry, cash, deposit, investment, liquidity gap, loan, negative relationship, ratio, total assets.

- Cluster 5, purple, consists of 8 topic items, namely: bank stability, deposit ratio, firm value, interest rate risk, net interest margin, observation, significant impact, significant negative effect.
- Cluster 6, light blue, consists of 3 topic items, namely: evidence, international banking, liquidity risk transmission.

Literature Review Study regarding Liquidity Risk Management in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

There are 6 research topics surrounding liquidity risk management, namely:

First, identify risks. Identification of liquidity risk in banking can be done by analyzing several factors, such as the amount of cash and cash equivalents available, deposit profile, quality of productive assets, and relationships with third parties such as other financial institutions or money markets. Apart from that, banks can also use tools such as liquidity ratios to measure the bank's ability to provide funds for timely customer withdrawals.

Second, risk measurement. There are several ways to measure liquidity risk in banking, including: (1) Liquidity Ratio, which is a ratio used to measure a bank's ability to provide funds for timely withdrawals of customer funds. The ratios used include the Current Ratio (CR) and Quick Ratio (QR); (2) Stress Testing, which is a method used to analyze how banks will react to unfavorable market conditions. Stress testing is carried out by assuming possible scenarios and analyzing the impact on the bank's liquidity position; (3) Net Stable Funding Ratio (NSFR), namely the ratio used to measure the bank's ability to provide long-term funds for long-term asset positions; (4) Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR), namely this ratio is used to measure the bank's ability to overcome emergency liquidity conditions. LCR measures how much cash and cash equivalents can be used to cover funds that must be disbursed within a 30 day period; (5) Intraday Liquidity Monitoring, which is a method used to measure bank liquidity in real-time so that it can identify potential liquidity problems before they occur.

Third, risk mapping. To map liquidity risk in banking, banking companies can use several methods, including: (1) Liquidity ratio analysis, namely measuring liquidity ratios such as the ratio of cost of funds to third party funds (CET1) and combined liquidity ratio (LCR); (2) Stress testing, namely simulating challenging economic scenarios to determine whether banking companies can overcome bad market conditions; (3) Real-time monitoring of market conditions to determine changes that may affect banking company liquidity; (4) Liquidity modeling in various scenarios to determine the potential impact of market changes or company policies; (5) Managing liquidity risk through activities such as risk limitation, purchasing insurance and investment diversification. All of these methods are used to understand and manage liquidity risk so that banking companies can overcome difficult market conditions and remain stable.

Fourth, risk management. Liquidity risk management in banking involves several stages, including: (1) Identification of liquidity risks, such as changes in interest rates, changes in economic conditions, or changes in banking activities; (2) Measuring the level of liquidity risk accepted by the bank, using methods such as stress testing or Value at Risk (VaR); (3) Controlling liquidity risk to reduce liquidity risk accepted by the bank, such as increasing liquidity reserves or reducing the amount of credit provided; (4) Continuously monitor liquidity conditions and take necessary action if liquidity risks change; and (5) Transparent and accurate reports and communications to authorities and stakeholders regarding liquidity risks accepted by the bank and actions taken to reduce these risks.

Fifth, risk monitoring. There are several ways to monitor liquidity risk in banking, including: (1) Monitoring liquidity ratios such as the liquidity reserve ratio (LCR) and net stable funding ratio (NSFR) can be used to monitor the health of bank liquidity; (2) Monitoring market movements and interest rates can provide information about liquidity risks that banks may face; (3) Monitoring the bank's financial position, including short-term and long-term assets and liabilities, can provide information about the liquidity risks that the bank may face; (4) Conduct sensitivity analysis to changes in factors that can influence bank liquidity, such as changes in interest rates, changes in financial markets, and changes in banking activities; (5) Carrying out stress testing to evaluate how the bank will survive in a bad economic situation that could potentially cause a liquidity crisis; and (6) Monitoring the rules and regulations applicable in banking to ensure compliance with compliance standards.

Sixth, risk control. There are several ways to control liquidity risk in banking, including: (1) Expanding the range of funding sources, namely banks can increase the diversification of funding sources by adding deposits, long-term loans and equity funds; (2) Managing changes in short-term

funding demand, namely banks can manage liquidity risk by identifying and anticipating changes in short-term funding demand; (3) Strengthening the risk supervision and management system, namely banks can strengthen the risk supervision and management system by establishing clear risk control procedures and implementing an effective risk monitoring system; (4) Creating liquidity reserves, namely banks can create liquidity reserves to be used in emergency situations that require banks to provide short-term funds quickly; (5) Utilizing money market instruments, namely banks can manage liquidity risk by utilizing money market instruments such as Bank Indonesia Certificates (SBI), Money Market Securities (SBPU), and Repo.

Literature Review Study regarding the Legal Basis for Liquidity Risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

There are 6 legal bases for liquidity risk management in Indonesia based on Bank Indonesia Regulations (PBI), namely: (1) BI Regulation No. 20/6/PBI/2011 concerning Application of Good Corporate Governance Principles in Banks; (2) BI Regulation No. 21/6/PBI/2011 concerning Liquidity Risk Management in Banks; (3) BI Regulation No. 22/12/PBI/2011 concerning Bank Liquidity Risk Reports; (4) BI Regulation No. 18/4/PBI/2013 concerning Liquidity Risk Management in Commercial Banks with Business Activities (BUKU) IV; (5) BI Regulation No. 19/7/PBI/2016 concerning Liquidity Risk Report for Commercial Banks with Business Activities (BUKU) IV; (6) BI Regulation No. 23/1/PBI/2018 concerning Implementation of Liquidity Risk Management Principles in Commercial Banks with Business Activities (BUKU) IV.

There are 4 legal bases for liquidity risk management based on the Financial Services Authority (OJK), which is the institution responsible for regulating and ensuring the stability of the financial system, including managing liquidity risk in banking. Several regulations issued by the OJK regarding liquidity risk in banking include: (1) OJK Regulation No. 18/POJK.03/2015 concerning Bank Liquidity, which regulates bank liquidity management and minimum liquidity standards that must be met by banks; (2) OJK Regulation No. 19/POJK.03/2015 concerning Net Stable Funding Ratio (NSFR), which regulates long-term liquidity ratios that must be met by banks; (3) OJK Regulation No. 20/POJK.03/2015 concerning Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR), which regulates short-term liquidity ratios that must be met by banks; (4) OJK Regulation No. 21/POJK.03/2015 concerning liquidity risk management, which regulates procedures for managing liquidity risk by banks.

There are 5 legal bases for liquidity risk management based on the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS). BCBS is a committee formed by the Board of Governors of the World Central Bank (Bank for International Settlements) which aims to increase the stability of the global banking system. BCBS has issued several regulations governing liquidity risk in banking in the world, including: first, Basel III Framework for Liquidity Risk Measurement, Standards and Monitoring (2010). Second, Basel III The Liquidity Coverage Ratio and liquidity risk monitoring tools (2013). Third, Basel III The Net Stable Funding Ratio (2014). Fourth, Basel III The Leverage Ratio (2014). Fifth, Basel III The Standardized Approach for measuring counterparty credit risk exposures (2014).

Literature Review Study regarding the Influence of Liquidity Risk on Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

There are 31 influences caused by liquidity risk, namely: (1) Asset Liability Management/ALM; (2) Abnormal Return; (3) audit fees; (4) selection of auditors; (5) bank stability; (6) BI Rate; (7) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR; (8) credit risk; (9) currency exchange rates; (10) economic growth; (11) financing; (12) financial crisis; (13) company value; (14) Gross Domestic Product/GDP; (15) government bonds; (16) Islamic Interbank Money Market/IIMM; (17) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR; (18) margins; (19) Mudharabah deposit products; (20) Non Performing Loans/NPL; (21) Operational Expenses to Operational Income/BOPO; (22) Price Earning Ratio/PER; (23) Price stability; (24) Return On Assets/ROA; (25) Return On Equity/ROE; (26) risk taking/risk-taking; (27) share price; (28) stock returns; (29) systematic risk; (30) Systemically Important Banks/SBIs; and (31) Total Assets.

Literature Review Study regarding Determinants of Liquidity Risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

There are 109 determinants of liquidity risk, namely: (1) Accounting Information Systems/AIS; (2) acquisition; (3) activity restrictions; (4) asset quality; (5) company age; (6) company policy; (7)

company capitalization; (8) Bank Capital Buffer/BCB; (9) competition between banks; (10) banking capital regulations; (11) banking growth; (12) inefficiency; (13) loan policy; (14) inter-banking network; (15) regulations; (16) banking portfolio; (17) company size; (18) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR; (19) cash ratio; (20) Chief Executive officer/CEO trust; (21) Cost-to-Income Ratio/CIR; (22) credit risk; (23) Cost of Funds/COF; (24) Covid-19; (25) cost efficiency; (26) Credit Loss Provision to Total Loans; (27) Current Liabilities to Net Worth; (28) deposit savings; (29) Loan Depositors; (30) Debt to Asset Ratio/DAR; (31) Debt to Equity Ratio/DER; (32) Dynamic Correlation; (33) Earning Assets to Total Assets of Bank; (34) Economic Freedom; (35) economic stability.

Next, are: (36) equity; (37) Equity to Total Assets/ETA; (38) External Financing Source/EFD; (39) External Funding to Total Liabilities; (40) family ownership; (41) Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR; (42) financial crisis; (43) financial expansion; (44) financial stability; (45) Financing Gap to Total Assets; (46) Financing Loss Provisions to Total Finance of Bank; (47) financing structure; (48) Fixed Charge Coverage; (49) foreign ownership; (50) global financial crisis; (51) Gross Domestic Product/GDP; (52) Hedging; (53) inflation; (54) income diversification; (55) information flow; (56) interbank loans; (57) investment; (58) Islamic Interbank Rate; (59) Leverage Ratio; (60) Lehman Crisis; (61) Liquid Assets to Deposit/LAD; (62) Liquid Assets to Total Assets/LATA; (63) Liquidity Coverage Ratio/LCR; (64) Liquidity Gap; (65) Liquidity Risk Management/LRM Index Method; (66) Liquidity Reserve to Total Assets; (67) Loan to Assets Ratio/LAR; (68) Loan Loss Reserves/LLR; (69) Loan Loss Provision to Loans/LLPL; (70) Long-Term Debt to Equity Ratio (LTDtER).

Next, are: (71) Long-Term Lending Interest Rate; (72) Loans to Total Assets/LTA; (73) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR; (74) market risk; (75) monetary policy; (76) money in circulation; (77) Net Interest Margin/NIM; (78) net profit; (79) Non Performing Financing/NPF; (80) Non-Performing Loans/NPL; (81) Net Working Capital/NWC; (82) Net Loans to Customers and Short-Term Funding; (83) Operational Expenses to Operational Income/BOPO; (84) Output Gap; (85) world oil prices; (86) owner's identity; (87) economy; (88) post-financial crisis; (89) private monitoring; (90) Return On Assets/ROA; (91) Return On Equity/ROE; (92) Real Estate Credit; (93) Legal Reserve Requirements/LRR or Minimum Statutory Reserve/GWM; (94) Risky Liquid Assets to Total Assets/RLA; (95) Supervisory Power; (96) government ownership; (97) stock market developments; (98) share price; (99) stock returns; (100) Systemic Banking Panics; (101) Volatility Spillovers; (102) Tangible Assets Debt Coverage; (103) technology; (104) Times Interest Earned; (105) Third-Party Funds or Third Party Funds/DPK; (106) threshold; (107) Total Finance to Total Assets; (108) Total Assets to Share Capital of Bank; and (109) Total Liabilities to Total Assets of Bank.

Literature Review Study regarding Liquidity Risk Measurement Methods in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

There are 34 research topics surrounding liquidity risk measurement methods, namely: (1) Artificial Neural Network; (2) Bayesian Network Model; (3) Basel III; (4) Balance Sheet Liquidity Analysis; (5) Big Data Analytics-Based; (6) Cash Capital Analysis; (7) Contingency Funding Flows; (8) Deposit-Loan Synergies Vary; (9) Exogenous liquidity risk models; (10) EGARCH-VaR; (11) Federal Reserve System; (12) Framework for the Application of Systems Thinking/FAST; (13) High-Order ES Based; (14) Independent Reviews of Internal Policies; (15) Islamic Financial Services Board/IFSB; (16) John Law-1705; (17) Liquidity Ratios and Limits; (18) Liquidity Stress Testing; (19) Liquidity Buffer; (20) Market Conditions; (21) Maturity Mismatch (GAP) Analysis; (22) Management of Foreign Currency Flows; (23) Multiperiod Bank Run Model; (24) Multi-Factor Risk Model; (25) Net Stable Funding Ratio/NSFR; (26) Option-Pricing Approach; (27) Panel Smooth Threshold Regression/PSTR; (28) Risk Assessment Model of Systemic Institutions; (29) Strengthening Information Systems; (30) Stress Testing; (31) Systemic Liquidity Risk Index/SLRI; (32) Systemic Decision Making; (33) Total Financing-to-Total Deposits and Short-Term Funding/LDEP; and (34) Walter Bagehot in 1873.

Literature Review Study regarding Liquidity Risk Disclosure in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

There are 6 research topics surrounding liquidity risk disclosure, namely:

First, the audit committee. Disclosure of liquidity risk by audit committees in banking is carried out through annual reports or bank financial reports. The audit committee will evaluate and audit the

liquidity risks faced by the bank, including the process of managing and supervising these risks. They will also provide recommendations for better risk controls and evaluate the effectiveness of existing risk controls.

Second, institutional ownership. Disclosure of liquidity risk in institutional holdings includes providing information about the types of assets held by the institution and how those assets can be used to meet liquidity obligations. It may also include information about the liquidity risk management protocols used by those institutions and how they evaluate and manage their liquidity risks. This information can usually be found in the institution's financial statements or in other documents issued by the institution.

Third, managerial ownership. Disclosure of liquidity risk in managerial ownership includes providing information about how company management manages and evaluates the company's liquidity risk. This may include information about the liquidity risk management protocols the company uses, as well as how the company manages relationships with banks and other lenders to meet its liquidity needs. This information can usually be found in the company's financial statements or in other documents published by the company, such as annual reports or financial performance reports.

Fourth, the proportion of independent commissioners. Disclosure of liquidity risk in the proportion of independent commissioners can be done through the company's financial report which includes information about the company's financial position, including its liquidity position. Independent commissioners can provide views and recommendations for managing company liquidity risk. In addition, companies can also provide information about liquidity risk management procedures and mechanisms implemented in annual reports or other reports issued to stakeholders.

Fifth, two-tuple linguistic representation. Two-tuple linguistic representation is a method for expressing risk using two elements, namely a word or phrase that expresses the level of risk and a word or phrase that expresses the level of confidence. For example, "high" can be used to express a level of risk and "certain" can be used to express a level of confidence. In liquidity risk disclosures, companies can use words or phrases such as "high" to express existing liquidity risks and "certain" to express the level of confidence that such risks will occur. This can be done in financial reports or other documents issued to company stakeholders.

Sixth, web-based. Disclosure of liquidity risk on a web-based basis can be done through the company's website which provides information about the company's financial position, including its liquidity position. The Company can provide information about implemented liquidity risk management procedures and mechanisms, as well as financial reports or other relevant reports which can be accessed via the website. Apart from that, the company can also provide a special page that provides information about liquidity risk and how the company manages this risk. The company can also provide real-time information about the company's liquidity position, which can be updated regularly via the company's website. Information that can be disclosed includes the company's current liquidity position, future liquidity projections, as well as the liquidity risk management mechanisms used by the company.

Literature Review Study regarding Liquidity Risk Mitigation in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

There are several topics surrounding liquidity risk mitigation issues, namely:

First, diversification. Diversification is one way to reduce liquidity risk in banking. Diversification can be done in various ways, such as: (1) Diversification of funding sources, namely banks can increase the diversification of funding sources by increasing deposits, increasing long-term loans, and increasing non-traditional income such as fee-based income; (2) Credit portfolio diversification, namely banks can increase credit portfolio diversification by increasing the number of customers, increasing the sectors or industries financed, and increasing the financing term; (3) Geographic diversification, namely banks can increase geographic diversification by increasing the number of branches in various regions or countries; (4) Product diversification, namely banks can increase product diversification by offering various banking products such as deposits, credit, and insurance and investment services; and (5) Risk diversification, namely banks can measure and manage risk using appropriate methods such as Value at Risk (VaR), Stress testing and Scenario Analysis. Overall, diversification can help banks to reduce liquidity risk by spreading risk across sectors, products and geographies. However, diversification also requires quite high costs and needs to be balanced with good risk management.

Second, forecasting cash flows. Cash flow forecasting is one way to reduce liquidity risk in banking. By doing this, banks can: first, improve liquidity planning, namely banks can improve liquidity planning by predicting cash flows in and out of the bank. This can help banks to identify potential liquidity problems before they occur and take preventive action beforehand. Second, improving liquidity monitoring, namely banks can improve liquidity monitoring by comparing the results of forecasting cash flows with actual conditions. This can help banks identify differences between forecasting results and actual conditions so they can take necessary action. Third, reducing liquidity risk, namely banks can reduce liquidity risk by predicting incoming and outgoing cash flows and taking preventive action beforehand. This can help banks to identify potential liquidity problems before they occur and take preventive action beforehand. Fourth, increase the efficiency of liquidity management, namely banks can increase the efficiency of liquidity management by predicting incoming and outgoing cash flows and taking preventive action beforehand. This can help banks to identify potential liquidity problems before they occur and take preventive action beforehand. Cash flow forecasting must also be carried out continuously and updated regularly to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the results obtained. In addition, it must also be carried out using appropriate and well-tested methods.

Third, Basel III version of risk management. Basel III is a regulatory standard issued by the Bank for International Settlements (BIS) which is aimed at increasing financial stability and reducing systematic risk in the banking industry. Mitigating liquidity risk in banking in accordance with Basel III includes: (1) Liquidity Coverage Ratio/LCR, namely a ratio that measures a bank's ability to face liquidity emergency situations by measuring the amount of liquid funds the bank has compared to the amount of funds needed in an emergency situation. Banks must meet the minimum LCR determined by the regulator; (2) Net Stable Funding Ratio/NSFR, which is a ratio that measures a bank's ability to meet long-term funding needs by measuring the amount of funds obtained from stable sources compared to the amount of funds used for long-term needs. Banks must meet the minimum NSFR determined by the regulator; (3) Stress testing, namely Basel III requires banks to carry out regular stress testing to measure the bank's ability to face liquidity emergencies. Stress testing is carried out by predicting the impact of various risk scenarios on the bank's liquidity position; (4) Disclosure, namely Basel III requires banks to provide sufficient and transparent information about the bank's liquidity position, including LCR, NSFR, and stress testing results; and (5) Intraday liquidity, namely Basel III also requires banks to meet intraday liquidity needs by providing sufficient facilities to address intraday liquidity needs that may arise between the netting and settlement cycles. Overall, Basel III provides a more comprehensive framework for reducing liquidity risks in banks, thereby strengthening the financial stability of the banking system as a whole.

Other liquidity risk mitigation includes: organized Tawarruq (commodity murabahah), short-term Sukuk Salam, International Islamic Liquidity Management (IILM) Short-Term Sukuk Program, and Financing Government Budget Deficit.

Literature Review Study of Countries That Have Implemented Liquidity Risk Management

There are several research countries that have implemented liquidity risk management, namely: Algeria, Austria, Australia, South Africa, Brazil, Canada, Chile, China, Czech, Cape Verde, Egypt, Israel, European Central Bank, France, Germany, Hong Kong, Indonesia, India, Iran, Iraq, Italy, Ireland, Japan, Jordan, Malaysia, Pakistan, Poland, Russia, Saudi, Sri Lankan, Thailand, Turkey, Tunis. United Kingdom, United States, Vietnam, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Morocco, Oman, Qatar, Syria, United Arab Emirates, Yemen, West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU) Banks and Western Balkans.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding liquidity risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions during the period 2006 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 289 research articles.
- The affiliate/institution that publishes the most research results is the IMF Economic Review, which is the institution that publishes the most journals that publish results on liquidity risk, with a total of 12 journal publications.

- The most productive researcher is: Syajarul Imna Moch. Amin from the Faculty of Economics and Management, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, who wrote 4 articles.
 - In the mapping visualization using the VOS viewer, research developments regarding liquidity risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions are divided into 6 clusters. Cluster 1 consists of 39 topics, cluster 2 consists of 32 topics, cluster 3 consists of 14 topics, cluster 4 consists of 13 topics, cluster 5 consists of 8 topics, and cluster 6 consists of 3 topics.
 - Based on a literature review, there are seven main research themes surrounding liquidity risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions, namely: (1) liquidity risk management; (2) legal basis; (3) the influence of liquidity risk; (4) determinants of liquidity risk; (5) liquidity risk measurement method; (6) disclosure of liquidity risks; and (7) liquidity risk mitigation.
- is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:
- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
 - The results of the e- review literature study can be explained in a more complex way.

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